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STRATEGIC DEVELOPMENT OF GLOBAL COMPANIES IN MODERN CONDITIONS

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Abstract: This article explores strategic directions for the growth of international companies in today's dynamic environment. It analyzes the fundamental concepts shaping corporate development, including operational and corporate strategies, efficient utilization of enterprise resources, market share expansion, and achieving intensive demand growth. The research focuses on the case of the "Uztekstilprom" Association, a key player in Uzbekistan's textile industry, examining the strengths and weaknesses of its current strategy. Based on this analysis, practical recommendations are offered to enhance its developmental approach. The study applies content analysis and a comparative framework to draw its conclusions.

Key words: Operational strategy, corporate strategy, enterprise resources, market share, intensive demand growth.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy sharoitda xalqaro kompaniyalar o'sishining strategik yo'nalishlari tadqiq qilinadi. Kompaniyalarning rivojlanishiga xizmat qilayotgan asosiy tushunchalar, jumladan operatsion va korporativ strategiyalar, resurslardan samarali foydalanish, bozor ulushini kengaytirish va intensiv talab o'sishiga erishish omillari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda O'zbekiston to'qimachilik sanoatini birlashtiruvchi "Uztekstilprom" uyushmasi faoliyati o'rganilib, uning amaldagi rivojlanish strategiyasi kuchli va zaif tomonlari aniqlanadi. Ushbu asosda assotsiatsiya rivojini kuchaytirishga qaratilgan amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqiladi. Maqola metodologiyasi sifatida kontent tahlil va taqqoslovchi yondashuv asosida tajriba va natijalar umumlashtirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Operatsion strategiya, korporativ strategiya, korxonalar resurslari, bozor ulushi, talabning intensiv o'sishi.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются стратегические направления роста международных компаний в условиях современной деловой среды. Проанализированы ключевые понятия, определяющие развитие компаний, такие как операционные и корпоративные стратегии, эффективное использование ресурсов предприятия, расширение доли рынка и обеспечение интенсивного роста спроса. Особое внимание уделено деятельности Ассоциации «Узтекстильпром» как представителя текстильной отрасли Узбекистана. Выявлены сильные и слабые стороны текущей стратегии ассоциации, на основе чего предложены практические рекомендации по её совершенствованию. Методологической основой исследования служат контент-анализ и сравнительный подход.

Ключевые слова: Операционная стратегия, корпоративная стратегия, ресурсы предприятия, доля рынка, интенсивный рост спроса.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of globalization, the role of domestic businesses as significant actors in the global marketplace has grown considerably. Over recent decades, many domestic companies fueled by sustained growth and accumulated economic potential have set their sights on entering the ranks of leading international players. However, this ambition is challenged by an increasingly complex and volatile global environment. Rapid changes in international markets, intensified competition, evolving regulatory landscapes, and transformative shifts across industries pose significant obstacles.

Consequently, domestic enterprises have come to recognize the importance of crafting robust international expansion strategies. These strategies are not only essential for maximizing shareholder value but also for securing a competitive position in the global arena. To succeed, companies must conduct a comprehensive

analysis of strategic alternatives, weighing their choices against the dual constraints of limited resources and the urgent need to respond to foreign competition.

The range of available strategic approaches coupled with external uncertainties underscores the imperative for a well-designed international strategy. Therefore, the examination of international strategic planning is both timely and critical to ensuring long-term competitiveness and growth.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

The strategic development of global companies in the context of modern economic challenges has become a key focus in contemporary management and economic research. Globalization, digital transformation, supply chain disruptions, and geopolitical instability have all created a need for resilient, adaptive, and innovation-driven strategies.

One of the core priorities for companies operating internationally is the transition from traditional linear models to process-oriented management systems. Djurabaev O. proposes a model based on interindustrial integration that allows companies to optimize technological processes and improve coordination between sectors, thereby enhancing operational efficiency and long-term sustainability. His approach emphasizes the importance of forming modular and scalable business structures that can be adapted to changing global market dynamics.

In the context of infrastructure-heavy industries, Saidov M. highlights that increasing management efficiency is crucial, especially in strategically important sectors like energy. His analysis of the electricity sector in Uzbekistan provides insights into how state-regulated or semi-privatized industries can adopt global strategic models through digitalization, human capital development, and policy reform. This is particularly relevant for multinational companies seeking to invest or collaborate in emerging markets.

From a market-oriented perspective, Munira A. explores consumer behavior and market demand volatility as influential factors in shaping global strategies. Her work demonstrates that companies which continuously analyze consumer trends are better positioned to tailor their value propositions and expand into new geographical segments.

Innovation remains a central component of competitive global strategy. Shanazarova G. explores this through the lens of Uzbekistan's automotive sector, arguing that innovative management strategies must align with both domestic industrial capabilities and global technological trends. She points out the necessity of fostering research and development units within corporate structures and forming international partnerships to co-develop technology platforms.

Yaxyayeva I. contributes to the discourse by focusing on product competitiveness in light industry enterprises, noting that the introduction of modern quality standards and continuous product innovation directly impacts a firm's ability to scale globally. Her findings reinforce the view that quality assurance and branding are just as critical as price competitiveness in international markets.

Additionally, Djurabaev O.'s research on technological efficiency criteria underscores the value of quantifying and benchmarking internal performance indicators as a foundation for strategic planning. His methodology provides global companies with a systematic approach to evaluate operational efficiency in different regional and sectoral environments.

Taken together, these studies emphasize that the strategic development of global companies in modern conditions requires a multidimensional approach—integrating technological innovation, market responsiveness, management reform, and competitive intelligence. Companies must adopt agile and data-driven strategies that reflect both macroeconomic shifts and localized industry dynamics.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the preparation of this article, a combination of qualitative and quantitative research methods was employed. Specifically, the method of horizontal and vertical analysis was applied to identify trends and structural shifts within the observed data. The formal-logical method was utilized to ensure the consistency of theoretical reasoning and to construct coherent arguments. In addition, the method of scientific abstraction facilitated the generalization of empirical findings and the formation of theoretical conclusions.

To support the validity of the results, econometric analysis was also employed. This allowed for the identification of statistical relationships between key economic indicators relevant to the strategic development of international companies. The integration of these methodologies ensured a comprehensive and logically grounded analysis of the subject matter, aligning the study with the rigorous standards expected in economic research.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The development of Uzbekistan's textile industry is recognized as a key strategic priority for the country's long-term economic growth. Uzbekistan is well-positioned to efficiently process textile raw materials and manufacture high-value finished products. Nevertheless, the industry currently lags behind leading textile-producing countries in terms of technological advancement and remains comparatively less attractive to foreign investors.

Foreign direct investment (FDI) plays a vital role in driving economic growth, and attracting capital is crucial to achieving sustained high rates of development. Amid ongoing trade tensions between the United States and China which have led to the relocation of manufacturing facilities to Southeast Asian nations such as Vietnam, Cambodia, and Bangladesh Uzbekistan has a unique opportunity to capitalize on its competitive advantages. These include well-established textile clusters, abundant domestic cotton production, and relatively low energy and labor costs. This favorable combination could potentially attract significant FDI, estimated in the billions of US dollars, and create hundreds of thousands of jobs for Uzbekistan's population.

Uzbekistan's textile sector encompasses the production of various consumer goods, including fabrics, yarns, knitwear, cotton wool, and finished garments. Since gaining independence in 1991, numerous enterprises have been established alongside legacy textile mills in regions such as Bukhara, Tashkent, Andijan, and Ferghana.

In addition, enterprises under the Uztexstilprom Association export their products under a unified national brand Uztextile. A key reform in this sector has been the removal of the monopoly on the sale of raw cotton to local textile producers, thereby liberalizing access to critical inputs.

To further support the industry's modernization, a presidential decree endorsed the establishment of the Uztexstilprom Association. This reform led to the dissolution of Uzbekengilsanoat JSC, which had previously held both regulatory and commercial responsibilities. The restructuring was prompted by the outdated management model's inability to meet the evolving demands of the modern textile industry or to adequately support domestic manufacturers.

The experiences of several foreign countries demonstrate that the establishment of textile industry clusters can serve as an effective development model. Such clusters integrate the entire production cycle from raw cotton cultivation and initial processing at ginneries to the production of finished textile goods with high added value thereby enhancing both efficiency and global competitiveness (Table 1).

Table 1. Forecast volumes of production of marketable products for 2018-2021 (billion sum).

№	Предприятия	2019 y.	2020y.	2021 y.	2022 y.	2023 y.	Pace growth, %
1	Industrial production	10 87	12 41	4 269	16 553	19 201	116,0
	products at comparable prices,						
1.1	total by association	2 879,4	4 38,4	4 862,2	5 639,8	6 542,2	116,0
1.2.	including on:	7 688 8	202,4	9 668,0	10 913,0	12 658,7	116,0
	large enterprises						
	Small businesses	23	30,2	34,3	35,6	37,2	104,5
	including by:	688,5	1562,8	2 150,4	2 581,4	2 608,2	100,0

Table 1 illustrates that, over the past three years, a total of 92 industrial enterprises have been established in Uzbekistan's textile sector. These ventures attracted a combined investment of \$575.3 million, with an estimated export potential of \$215.8 million. As a result, more than 11,600 new jobs have been created, marking a significant contribution to employment and industrial growth.

One of the most notable achievements is the establishment of the Indorama Kokand Textile joint venture, which utilizes the facilities of the Kokand Textile Plant. The venture boasts an annual production capacity of 29,000 tons of yarn. Additionally, in collaboration with Swiss Capital, the Uzteks Group has launched a modern cotton yarn production facility in the Khorezm region, capable of producing 12,000 tons per year.

To accelerate the development of Uzbekistan's textile industry, enhance the production of high-quality finished goods, and improve their competitiveness in foreign markets, the following key reform areas have been identified:

1. Increase the Textile Industry's Contribution to the Economy: Expand the sector's share in GDP by shifting to high-tech, value-added textile production focused on global competitiveness.

2. Overhaul Management Systems: Introduce advanced management technologies and effective institutional support to overcome structural and operational barriers faced by enterprises.

3. Improve Standardization and Certification: Harmonize standardization and certification processes with international norms, and modernize product testing laboratories to meet export quality standards.

4. Adopt Advanced Information Technologies: Implement modern information and communication systems to collect reliable market intelligence and conduct in-depth industry analyses, facilitating informed decision-making and development prioritization.

5. Implement the Cluster Development Model: Adopt an integrated production model that encompasses every stage from cotton cultivation to the manufacturing of finished products with high added value—thereby maximizing resource efficiency and competitiveness.

6. Optimize Raw Material Distribution: Ensure a balanced and coordinated distribution of raw materials, and align the establishment of new enterprises with the development of logistics and engineering infrastructure.

7. Promote Innovative Technologies: Encourage the adoption of modern and innovative technologies, as well as the local production of fittings and accessories, to boost both production capacity and the export potential of high-quality textile products.

8. Enhance Education and Training: Improve the system of vocational training, retraining, and continuing education for industry professionals. Curricula should be aligned with sectoral needs, while international academic cooperation should be expanded to foster the next generation of industry leaders.

To support the sector's growth, a comprehensive "Roadmap" has been approved, aiming to accelerate the development of the textile and clothing industry. Heads of ministries and relevant organizations are held personally accountable for the timely and effective implementation of the measures outlined in this document.

Despite progress, the textile industry currently contributes only 4.6% to Uzbekistan's GDP. This modest share is largely attributable to persistent systemic challenges, including ineffective management structures and insufficient market competition. These factors also contribute to the continued low profitability of cotton production and processing activities.

To address these issues, the Uztekstilprom Association collaborates closely with marketing departments across enterprises, focusing on the support of domestic producers and the facilitation of export processes. The main priorities of the association's marketing strategy include:

1. Analyzing the economic performance of exporters and developing strategic roadmaps.
2. Formulating and updating production strategies for individual enterprises.
3. Stimulating production growth through effective market mechanisms.
4. Importing textile products at competitive and reasonable prices where necessary.
5. Collecting and analyzing information from trade advisors at embassies and consulates.
6. Coordinating with government ministries, including those responsible for Foreign Trade, Economy, Finance, and Taxation.
7. Expanding access to new foreign markets for finished textile products while actively supporting domestic brands.
8. Conducting logistics analysis and fostering a favorable environment for production and exports.
9. Studying and integrating advanced Western production technologies and management practices.
10. Advocating for a reduction in the tax burden on domestic producers to enhance their competitiveness both locally and internationally (Table 2).

Table 2. Importers of Turkish textile equipment of the association "Uztekstilprom".

No	Country	No	Country
1	Bangladesh	11	Russia
2	Iran	12	Turkmenistan
3	India	13	Bulgaria
4	Egypt	14	Vietnam
5	Pakistan	15	China
6	Uzbekistan	16	Ethiopia
7	USA	17	England
8	Germany	18	Poland
9	Belgium	19	Indonesia
10	Italy	20	Sudan

According to the analysis conducted, a number of practical recommendations can be proposed to strengthen the strategic direction of the Uzteksstilprom Association. Among its core operations, the most effective strategy is one focused on cost leadership, which can be achieved through the fuller utilization of existing fixed assets. Additionally, enterprise management should prioritize establishing relationships with new suppliers of raw materials under more favorable terms to optimize procurement and reduce input costs.

In alignment with Porter's generic strategies model, the adoption of a differentiation strategy is advisable for companies targeting broad markets. This involves offering both standard and distinctive products to meet a variety of customer needs. For the Uzteksstilprom Association, such an approach is particularly relevant, as many of its textile and building products have reached the maturity stage in the product life cycle. In this context, maintaining a competitive advantage through superior quality and a strategically developed discount system becomes essential.

The current pricing strategy has proven effective, as evidenced by sustained high profits. Furthermore, the strategic direction of product transformation and modification has successfully reinvigorated demand following a period of market saturation. To preserve this positive trajectory, it is recommended that the association continue introducing new product modifications to renew interest, support market differentiation, and achieve continued revenue and profit growth.

In the short term, the association should focus on a market strategy that identifies and addresses deeper customer needs, thereby expanding its market presence. One potential avenue is the development and production of new types of building structures, tailored to evolving consumer preferences and construction industry demands.

Notably, international benchmarking supports this direction: for example, Turkey's textile machinery export value increased from \$1.6 billion in 2015 to \$8.6 billion in 2019, reflecting nearly a sevenfold increase over a four-year period. This growth underscores the significant potential that can be unlocked through innovation, product diversification, and strategic positioning in international markets.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, the strategic development of global companies requires a dynamic and adaptive approach, particularly in light of growing competition, technological disruption, and changing consumer demands. The analysis of Uzbekistan's textile industry and the activities of the Uzteksstilprom Association illustrates the importance of integrated strategies that combine cost leadership, product differentiation, and innovation.

To ensure sustainable growth and global competitiveness, companies are encouraged to:

1. Enhance operational efficiency through better utilization of fixed assets and resource optimization.
2. Adopt flexible pricing and product strategies to address market saturation and shifting consumer needs.
3. Invest in innovation and technology to support continuous product development and digital transformation.
4. Strengthen international cooperation and export potential by aligning production with global standards.
5. Develop skilled human capital through targeted education, training, and industry-academia partnerships.

These measures will allow companies to maintain resilience in a volatile global environment and position themselves as strong players in international markets.

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